

Social Collectivism and Existentialists (Ubuntu) Ideology: Panacea For Improved and Sustainable Standard of Living among Vulnerable Citizens in Nigeria

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Abstract

African ideology of social collectivism, inclusiveness, and communism is primarily derived from the 'Ubuntu ideology' the innate and natural instinct of humans to render help to others and allows every member of the society to exist in a collective and mutually sustaining environments. Social collectivism (Ubuntu) is a multidimensional existentialist model of development that guarantees continuity and sustainability through collective efforts and participatory approaches. Collectivism and existentialist ideology recognize the need for meaningful cohesive community engagement in improving the lives of citizens. Vulnerable people are the weak, the infirmed, the sick, deprived, the neglected and abandoned, usually physically and emotionally challenged persons, the exceptional persons and less privileged in society. These vulnerable populations especially in Nigeria and Africa in general suffer untold hardship which can be addressed principally by relying on the ubuntu ideological orientation of; 'we exist because you exist', which is fundamental and germane to human existence. This paper, therefore, adopts a descriptive and theoretical methodology in examining "social collectivism and existentialist ideology as a panacea for the improved sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens in Nigeria. It places emphasis on the interconnectedness of its application for group and short-term social and psychotherapy in human development and learning informed by relying on group-oriented approaches rather than individualism. Particular attention will be focused on the influence of Ubuntu in meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and sustaining its gains in humanitarianism. The paper concludes that social collectivism and existentialist ideology are essential in building relationships giving meaning to existence, and improving a sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens, and recommends that groups' interconnectedness should be promoted as a strategy for promoting and improving sustainable standard of living of vulnerable populations in Nigeria.

Keyword: *Social collectivism, Existentialist, Ubuntu, Vulnerable citizens, Sustainable standards*

Introduction

The world is in constant flux, laced with social problems and humanitarian emergencies created by human interactions with nature and the environment creating imbalances and challenges in society. Many people for one reason or the other fall victim to circumstances and are disadvantaged. Thus, they are categorized as vulnerable populations and citizens. Existence and Life only have meaning when we interact with one another in a mutually inclusive manner. The essence of existence generally is impactful when we live for one another, and when we are multiple prisms in providing solutions to 'order' the society and thus, addressing one of the Hobbesian existentialist questions; "*How is life and or society possible*". All through human existence and interactions, problem-solving has remained one of the most important and herculean tasks in society because all attempts to create and stimulate sustainable growth and development and improve the living standard of citizens are accompanied by socioeconomic and cultural problems needing specific interventions and solutions.

Man's existence and daily activities have brought about lots of challenges; social, economic, cultural, religious, environmental, and geographical problems. These challenges have inadvertently affected the serenity, security, peace, and the pace of development of society in diverse ways and have in no small measure affected the living conditions of the citizens. The

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magnitude and impact of these problems make it even more difficult for individuals, groups, families, and communities to handle unaided thus, necessitating collective intervention by, groups, local, national, regional, and international bodies; like the Community-Based Organizations (CBOs), and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), World Bank, UNICEF, UNESCO, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). However, within this macro-organizational outlook, there are webs of microcosmic building networks that promote inclusiveness, collectivity, and unity of purpose which depicts the ubuntu ideology and philosophy. Families, groups, and communities like these macro-organizations play key leading roles during humanitarian emergencies, from the provision of food to security, economic recovery, and safeguarding the environment, caring for the sick and vulnerable in society. Man, in essence, is a product of interaction and relationship which gives meaning the life, therefore care and services have been in existence in Africa since the pre-historic and medieval periods and inherent in man. Certain problem-solving approaches and strategies have been used within the African context which have yielded many results in solving problems while other methods proved counterproductive because of not taking into confidence the interconnectedness and collectiveness of people, their space, and the environment of others as participants and collaborators in advancing social and economic benefits in society. But what has consistently not failed is the reliance on the ‘building blocks’ of the African survival and ideological creation, the Ubuntu philosophy, ‘*we are because you are*’, the bond of unity and commitment to one another. The concept of ubuntu is an alternative to individualistic and utilitarian ideologies that tend to dominate the Western world. It is this belief in collectiveness, cohesion, and community existence that makes Africa and Africans different from other races and continents, and even more plausible in managing and solving social problems within the society, especially as they affect vulnerable populations. The ideology supports collectivism over individualism.

Vulnerability is a convergence of risk, measured in and by four key dimensions that relate and connect empathy, integrity, adaptability, and authentic leadership, for trusted working environments. These key dimensions of empathy, integrity, adaptability, and leadership are inextricably the driving force of successful intervention practices and managing vulnerable populations. To a very large extent, every individual in society is vulnerable at one point or the other. Vulnerable population according to Wikipedia (2018), refers to the quality or state of being exposed to the possibility of being attacked or harmed either physically, socially emotionally, and economically. It involves some risk combined with the level of social and economic liability and the ability to cope with the resulting events. It often emanates from non-inclusiveness and non-participation in development, and care agendas, deprivation, poverty, and lack and or poor access to basic needs and services especially health, education, water and sanitation, security, and safe environment in tune with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 1- Poverty; 2-Zero hunger; 3-Good health and wellbeing; 4- Quality education; 5-Gender equity; 8-Descent work environment; 10-Reduce inequality, 11- Sustainable cities and communities; 15-life on land, and 16- peace and justice strong institutions. Other factors that influence social problems are natural and man-made disasters, crises, and the absence or non-existent strong judicial and political institutions.

Espousing the Existentialists (Ubuntu) ideology in Nigeria:

In all Nigerian and African societies, the idea and the concepts of ‘*We or Ours*’ and ‘*we rise by lifting others collectively*’ is an organic and functional solidarity that existed from ancient times. Nigeria's cultural and religious beliefs and practices are anchored on the philosophy of collectiveness, togetherness, and inclusiveness which makes the people of Nigeria and African descent unique and distinctive in all interactions and relationships. The concept of existentialism (ubuntu) is a concrete claim that the starting point for all actions is human existence and the meaning created out of it (Asouzu 2004). This is a compelling group dynamic model derived from the idea “*we exist because you exist*” which can be likened to “*one for all, all for one*” This indeed is what makes Nigerians and Africans bold and pronounced in terms of helping to meet family, group, individuals, and community’s needs as well as help others to survive. This hand-holding philosophy provides and enhances participation and inclusiveness in decision-making and in providing sustained living standards and livelihood options for family, group, and community members. Africans from Nigeria, South Africa, Uganda, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Kenya, Congo, Guinea, Ghana, Liberia, Malawi, etc., are fixated on the idea of community living building a network of sustainable approaches to promote communal living standards and lifting and assisting others to meet their needs. This means that man is always in the process of creating meaning, making himself, and facing his choices. That man possesses human nature which is the conception of a human being, and is found in every man. Thus, this collective coexistence (ubuntu) approach strengthens partnership opportunities for vulnerable citizens and populations, the poor, and the weak in society.

According to some of the foremost pan- African leading icons in African identity and by far the biggest advocate of Ubuntu, Archbishop Emeritus Desmond Tutu (2000), Dr. Kenneth Kaunda of Zambia, Julius Nyerere of Tanzania, and Nelson Mandela of South Africa, Nnamdi Azikiwe and Obafemi Awolowo, Anthony Enahoro, Bishop Samuel Ajayi Crowther who

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had consistently seen social collectivism as a moral compass of communism and ideological creation to pursue and improve the standard of living. Ubuntu emphasizes collectivism the sacredness of human life and the centrality of the community in meeting individual, group, and community needs. Like the Indian and Portuguese “*Ahimsa*” practiced by the Hindus, Buddhists, and Jainism, as a doctrine of non-violence, concerned with the sacredness of all living things and the effort to avoid causing harm to others is a derivative of social collectivism (ubuntu) ideology. In Nigeria and Africa in general, the sanctity and sacredness of life are not detached from man’s interactions and communication especially when compared to acclaimed Western culture and civilization. If one considers the fact that, Egypt was the cradle of civilization and center of commerce during the pre-industrial and medieval eras, the Industrial Revolution and Renaissance periods point to the fact that the Nigerian economy and social network systems were anchored on collectivism and communism which are ubuntu model in coalescing efforts to promote inclusiveness and enhance participation among the populace, thus improving the standard of living. Ubuntu preaches communism, unlike the European and American social and economic determinism which are consciously detached from the shelves of humanism and communism because of their socialist and capitalist orientations. Within the African and Nigerian soil, virtually every society practice communism and explores ubuntu philosophy as an approach to meeting their needs, especially the vulnerable citizens, and what could be considered as ‘ubuntu descent’ though in different co-names. For example, among the ‘*Yako-Ekoi*’ tribe of southern Nigeria, the doctrine of ubuntu is known and referred to as ‘*amon-amon*’ a concept that convokes a sense of love, belongingness, partnership, and mutual protection.

All over the African continent, and Nigeria in Particular, the term ‘ubuntu’ is traceable to many African societies, as it is used to express bonding or affiliation with others. According to Mugumbate and Nyanguru (2013), and Mbigi (2005), Ubuntu is derived from the Nguni and Bantu languages of Africa. In the Zulu language of South Africa, the word symbolizes being human. This meaning is also expressed in other languages. In Shona, a Zimbabwe language, the word unhu means the same thing. The same meaning is expressed by Ubuthosi in Ndebele, another Zimbabwe language. In Botswana, the word both expresses the same meaning whilst, in Tanzania, it is ubuntu. Congo, Angola, Makwi, Mozambique and Uganda use the words bomotu, gimuntu, umunthu, vumuntu and umuntu respectively. Similarly, in Kinyarwanda, the mother tongue in Rwanda, and Kivundi, the mother tongue in Burundi, Ubuntu means human generosity as well as ‘humanity’ in Runyakifara, the collection of dialects spoken by the Banyankore, Banyoro, Bafooro, and Bakiga of Western Uganda and also the Bahaya, Banyambo, and others of Northern Tanzania, Ubuntu refers to the human characteristics of generosity, protection, consideration and humaneness towards others in the community.

Existentialists (Ubuntu) ideology: Conceptual clarification

Ubuntu echoes the African thought of acceptable ideas and deeds, ideas that reflect a sense of bonding and unity, a sense of community. According to Mugumbate and Nyanguru (2013), Ubuntu can best be described as humanism from the African perspective as proposed by the former head of the Zambian government, Dr. Kenneth Kaunda. Thus, Ubuntu is Africa’s world view of societal relations, social collectivism, and existentialism. It is a social and humanistic ethic, a prism of enthusiastic social relations and engagement that enhances collectivism. The word social collectivism (ubuntu) can be described as the capacity in the African culture to express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, cooperation, sympathy, humanity, and mutuality in the interests of building and maintaining communities with justice and mutual caring (Khoza 2006:6; Mandela 2006:444; Tutu 1999:34-35). This view of Ubuntu expresses in totality the innate beauty, perception, belief, and dignity with which the Africans (s) shared among themselves as collective beings before it was colonized. Africans see each other of different tribes and origins as one sharing the same heritage and ideology. Similarly, the New World encyclopedia sees Ubuntu as embodying all those virtuous that maintain harmony and the spirit of sharing among members of a society. Thus, it implies an appreciation of traditional beliefs, cultural patterns, and distinct practices, and a constant awareness that an individual’s actions today are a reflection of the past and will have far-reaching consequences for the future not only to the individual, family, or group but also the society.

Furthermore, Nelson Mandela (former President of South Africa) describes Ubuntu as a philosophy constituting a universal truth, a way of life, which underpins an open society (Mandela, 2006). A society that is open to ideas, changes, and actions that can promote oneness, in terms of the development, growth, and sustenance of the society. This is similar to the Mahatma Gandhi *Ahimsa* of India. This could be further expanded to mean a society based on inclusiveness, one in which every member is a reflection and mirror of the other members and the society, participating fully and actively towards achieving a common goal with love, sincerity, fairness, equity, justice, and empathy to the vulnerable population, and non-violence. It is a movement of consciousness devoid of prejudices and imbued with a sense of equity and justice.

Existentialist (Ubuntu) ideology and Vulnerable Citizens

Vulnerability refers to the unavailability of protection which renders people, families, organizations, and societies incapable to withstand adverse conditions and impact from multiple stressors when they are exposed. Vulnerability is most likely being exposed to the chance of being attacked or harmed physically or emotionally, socially, and economically thus rendering the victims powerless, helpless, defenseless, and unguarded. Vulnerability is both structural and situational, often as a result of lack of access to basic existent political representation or power. Due to its versatility, the word vulnerability can be discussed in different areas of endeavors, such as health, education, economics, religion, social and environmental. In the words of Zakour and Gillespic (2013); and Cohn (2016), vulnerability can also be attributed to the way the lives of different groups are structured and shaped by structural patterns based on politics, economics, environmental management practices, race and class relations, the gender-based divisions of labour and other factors. According to Yolanda (2022), a vulnerable population is a term used to describe a group of people who possess some sort of disadvantage. These disadvantages could be social, physical, security, economic, health, etc. Similarly, David and Tanner (2007) see a vulnerable population (citizens) as a population that is highly susceptible to harm, and this can result from interactions between the resources available to individuals and communities, and the life challenges they face. These challenges hinder their collective goal attainment and compromises their existence, limiting and preventing the vulnerable citizens from accessing or performing task unaided as well as meeting their needs and improving their living conditions.,

Thus, vulnerability results from developmental problems, personal incapacities, disadvantaged economic and social relations, the inadequacy of interpersonal networks and supports, degraded neighborhoods and environments, poor or unavailable linkages to build synergy and partnership, and the complex interactions of these factors over the life course. Thus, by implication, every member of a population is susceptible and vulnerable in one aspect or the other. The difference could be that some persons are more susceptible than others or are faced with various degrees of vulnerability.

What Constitute Key Vulnerable Populations

The complexity of life, generally speaking, makes everyone potentially vulnerable over an extended period, due to the differential susceptibility to predisposing factors and risks. Some individuals and groups of the population face greater risk than others and respond to these dislocations of both physical and emotional issues differently, due to some functional and dysfunctional systems in the society. These groups according to Leiyu (2001); Aday (1994); and Lurie (1997), represent diverse groups of individuals who experience wide disparity in access to education, health care, and economic and cultural services and outcomes, and higher relative risk of poor physical, psychological, and/or social health than the population as a whole. This is what makes collective intervention a panacea for the sustainable standard of living for these categories of the population. An intervention anchored on the ideology of interconnectedness, reciprocity, communism, and mutual relationship.

There are many dimensions and classifications of the vulnerable population but there is no definite characteristic classification of key vulnerable populations. This is because every individual in the population experiences one form of vulnerability or the other. However, scholars and the United Nation High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR), (2006), has identified the following populations that can be considered key vulnerable population: These are a group of people who may be physically, mentally, or educationally, economically socially disadvantaged and who may be unable to meet their basic needs and may therefore require specific assistance. Assistance that may likely come from within the community groups or otherwise;

1. Persons exposed to and/or displaced by conflict or natural hazards.
2. Individuals who are cognitively impaired, including those who may not be capable of giving informed consent or standing trial.
3. Children, youth, and women
4. Individuals who are homeless or living in unstable housing situations and loss of income and revenue
5. Those in correctional institutions/prisoners, parolees, and probationers
6. Children in foster care or unstable home environments.
7. Individuals with mental health issues and disorders, particularly those with active psychoses, major depression, suicide ideation, self-harming behaviors, and addiction.
8. Individuals with chronic or acute illness or conditions; medically underserved or underinsured.
9. Caregivers and others who may be especially subject to secondary Post Traumatic Stress Disorders (PTSD) or burnout.
10. Individuals experiencing trauma, violence, abuse, or bullying
11. Individuals who may be at risk for coercion such as students and employees

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12. Elderly individuals, particularly those in assisted living or nursing homes or with intersecting risk factors.
13. Individuals who are socioeconomically or educationally disadvantaged.
14. Individuals from communities of color or indigenous or immigrant communities, particularly when studies focus on experiences of discrimination.
15. Individuals who have engaged in criminal activities, including the use of illegal substances, prostitution, or sexual trafficking and crime.

Other classification of the vulnerable population includes children themselves as children, exceptional children, forcefully and internally displaced persons, the emergent and abject poor, and those in abusive marriage and relationships as well as those with employment issues.

Problems with Vulnerable Populations

Our society is braided with complexities resulting from everyday natural and human activities and interactions; social, economic, educational, agricultural, cultural, religious, information, and technological activities which inadvertently create flux and imbalances in society. One would, therefore, say the problems of the vulnerable populations are the creation and function of the society itself. These problems form the nucleus and value of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) initiative; they include by not limited to the following:

1. Problems of finding safe, affordable housing as most of them live in crowded conditions and places as well as a safe environment
2. Problems of reliable means of transportation to their various areas of endeavors such as work, school, farms, markets, healthcare facilities, etc.
3. Hunger, starvation poor feeding, and general poverty.
4. Problem of unemployment and underemployment. These have contributed to poor financial security which in turn increases vulnerability.
5. Inadequate physical, social security, and insurance, and poor government attention or presence.
6. Susceptibility to diseases and illness as a result of poor access to medication, nutrition, poor sanitation, and a healthy environment.
7. Partnership opportunities to achieve reliable goal
8. The problem of achieving Peace and justice strong intuitions
9. Equitable resource allocation and distribution among the populations
10. Inequality gender disparity and discrimination
11. Sustainable communities and societies where equity and justice prevail
12. Problem of illiteracy poor education, and infrastructural development
13. Building innovative and supportive infrastructures and institutions that enhance the lives of disadvantaged and challenged persons.
14. The problem of creating pathways and linkages to resource systems, opening up opportunities, and promoting partnership and synergy among individuals, groups, and communities.

Existentialist (Ubuntu) Ideology as a Social Therapy for Vulnerable Citizens

The Ubuntu philosophy according to Mbigi, (1997; 1995), Van Den Heuvel, Mangalis & Van de Bunt, (2006:48), represents an African conception of human beings and their relationships with the community that embodies the ethics defining Africans and their social behavior. Nigeria as a major component of the African heritage is equally known to have developed these social collectivism and existentialist orientations as part of its national cultural outlook. They explain that Africans are social beings that are in constant communion with one another in an environment where a human being is regarded as a human being only through his or her relationships with other human beings According to Tutu in Battle (1997:39-43). Therefore, the survival of a human being, especially the vulnerable population is dependent on other people, the community, and society at large. The ecosystem interaction is based on political, social, economic, environmental, cultural, and religious determinants which centrifugal forces in vulnerability and shape the sphere of intervention in these regards. Managing vulnerable populations is a complex web of processes that are tailored towards promoting sustainable livelihood. These approaches follow a pattern of assessment modalities, social inquiry, and implementation considered against specific weaknesses, opportunities, and likely threats (SWOT), and specific, measurable, achievable, reliable, and timely (SMART) interventions theory and application. The underlying ubuntu interventions towards vulnerable populations are equally anchored on SWOT and SMART concepts. This intervention matrix allows for effective and efficient monitoring and evaluation of interventive procedures, documentation, and

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reportage, and provides a feedback mechanism for assessing outcomes, budgeting, and scaling up interventions as well as providing avenues for strengthening decisions, implementation strategy, and re-planning. This is the hallmark of Ubuntu's ideology in managing vulnerable populations, which relates to Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory.

By and large, Ubuntu portrays everything good and beautiful and seeks a healthy and peaceful society for all, an egalitarian and just society where every member of society is capable of realizing their potential.

1. Ubuntu and love for the vulnerable: Love in this context is described as an extension of deep affection and goodwill to every member of society. Just as the popular saying "Love your neighbor as you love yourself", Ubuntu preaches compassion, empathy, and communion with others. Just as an individual would want everything good for himself, the Ubuntu philosophy endeavors to see vulnerable populations not as an isolated group to be treated differently, but as an extension of a family whose needs and care are of great concern. This according to Samkange and Samkange (1980), is a virtue encompassed and embedded in Ubuntu. We must continue to be our brother keepers irrespective of the challenges and demands at hand. Children of the society in this context are never orphans. They are and belong to the community and as such must be taken care of by those who profess Ubuntu whether closely related or not.
2. Ubuntu and Social Justice for the vulnerable: SDGs Goal 16 particularly emphasizes peace and justice in strong institutions to promote equity and fair play in human interactions and to give members of the society hope for an egalitarian society irrespective of culture, creed, race, or language. Building strong justice institutions and an egalitarian society that will guarantee and enhance democratic processes and equal opportunity to all categories of people in the society. Institutions that promote quality education, good health, and well-being. According to Proven, Du Toit, and Engelbrecht, (2006), the practice of Ubuntu unlocks the capacity of an African culture in which individuals express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, humanity, and mutuality in the building and maintaining communities with justice and communalities. Social justice according to Obeten (2021), refers to the application of justice in a social context concerning how society is organized how people relate with one another, and the extent to which they have responsibilities towards one another. Thus, the essence of social justice is to provide and ensure even distribution of resources that will benefit the generality of the public and opposed to sectionalization or individualization as professed by the apostles and disciples of capitalism (Obeten 2021). Social justice is therefore embedded in the ubuntu ideology and explains why collective responsibility is central to Africans. Therefore, ubuntu speaks of communal living and a social justice system that involves group support, sharing of resources, and cooperation. These also extend to sharing burdens at difficult moments with the view of finding and solving challenges as they arrive. The social justice system as preached by Ubuntu philosophy, creates a balanced scale for actions and intervention and vulnerable populations are ensured of a fair deal in resource allocation and an all-inclusive conflict resolution mechanism based on justice, equity, and fairness. Justice is sought out at community bases and is restorative where justice is seen to be served and the bearer being compensated equally.
3. Ubuntu and Security/Protection of the Vulnerable Population: Vulnerability threatens the security of the larger population both economically and socially. Every breakdown, lawlessness, mischief, and compromise of security architecture in society is tied to the failure of the community to represent itself through communal engagement by the people's failure to recognize their strengths and weaknesses. Most of the threat to peaceful coexistence is due largely to joblessness, underemployment, scarcity of resources untold poverty, and lack of or inadequate access to resource systems and linkages. Thus, exposing vulnerable populations and denying them their fundamental and inalienable rights spells a doom for their collective existence and enterprise.
4. A typical example of a failed social justice system is the 2021 protest against the Nigeria Police Force - End Special Armed Robbery Squad (ENDSARS), the protest that was hijacked by politicians and hoodlums to wreak havoc in the society, public, and government infrastructures.
5. The application Ubuntu model is to enhance collective social and conventional security and insurance for its members including the weak, the vulnerable, and the strong. These categories of vulnerable people can be connected or linked to unemployment benefits, pensions, and gratuity, work compensation benefits, etc., for self-reliance and even community development. Ubuntu adopts the military dictum 'An injury to one is an injury to all'. That means every member of the community irrespective of class, status, creed, color, race, culture and religion to be treated on an equal basis. The community with prejudices is constituted and expected to stand shoulder to shoulder with all its members in all circumstances and situations. There is solidarity and concern for its members who are bereaved or confronted with one challenge or the other. These according to Broodryk (2005) include visiting sick people who are not necessarily one's relatives, sending condolences to a bereaved family, adopting an orphan as one's child, providing food for the needy in the community, assisting the elderly in many ways, and greeting others in a loving, friendly and compassionate way.

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6. Ubuntu and Good Governance for the Vulnerable Population: In every society, the administrative structure and governance strategy play a key leading role in the sustainability of the society. The principles of ubuntu underscore the importance of good governance because it promotes acceptance, confidence, partnership, trust, probity, and equitability in resource management and human development. Good governance, which is intertwined with business ethics, is considered critical in organizational practice, as well as in general corporate productivity (Rossouw, 2005:105). The founding principles of business ethics and corporate governance are in line with the Ubuntu philosophy of regarding all members of an organization as part of the community. It is this direct involvement of and with community members that brings about greater solidarity, love, caring, and sharing within a grouping and organization.

A major governance challenge in current governance issues has been corruption, which reveals the moral depravity and badness of the perpetrators (Broodryk, 2005; Moloketi, 2009; Nyarwath, 2002). Generally, corruption is caused by a lack of commitment to moral beliefs by the perpetrators, which in turn is due to weak value systems and the moral will of an individual towards other people. Corruption is a moral issue and blight to sustainable development especially, where the perpetrators are fundamentally and fantastically corrupt, as Prime Minister of England Boris Johnson described Nigeria in 2018. This suggests insensitivity on the part of the government to meet the needs of her citizenry in raising their standard of living. It presupposes a negative dive and a departure from positive curves of development expected to trickle down to the populace. Such a moral issue affects human life in a negative way where individuals abuse their personal and official powers (Broodryk, 2005:198). Corruption comes in different forms, which include nepotism, misuse of power, favoritism, and bribery, as well as prejudices and compromises. While corruption manifests itself in the relationship between individuals and institutions, as a practice, it is mostly rooted in the operations of market forces (Moloketi, 2009:239). Unlike the Ubuntu teaching, corruption is a pursuit of individual prosperity, as opposed to the common good of all and society. Corruption erodes the common fabric, undermines community perpetuates poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment, and further widens the economic and social gaps between the various class structures. Ultimately, corruption leads to a rise in the blatant pursuit of individual gains. When the awareness of moral rights and wrongs is strong, corruption can easily be rooted out. This is the principle behind the community-based Ubuntu philosophy. To curb corruption, for instance, the Ubuntu philosophy must be the essence of a value system that underpins a commitment to eliminate corruption (Moloketi, 2009:243, 247). There is also a need for strong robust democracies, where all sectors of society, including the media and organizations of civil society, the private sector, trade unions, traditional leaders, and faith-based organizations have a responsibility to educate and promote the values of Ubuntu philosophy and anti-corruption. The above observations indicate that there is much that the Ubuntu philosophy can contribute towards business ethics and good corporate governance issues. Under the African Ubuntu philosophy, people should be aware that individualism greed, and profit achieved by sacrificing other community members, contravenes the true foundations of humanity (Ubuntu). The notion of Ubuntu or humanity teaches community and organic solidarity, caring, and sharing among the members of a community or organization.

Conceptualization of the problem

Man's existence and daily activities have brought about lots of challenges; social, economic, cultural, religious, environmental, and geographical problems. These multifaceted challenges have seriously affected the serenity, security, peace, and the development of society in diverse ways and further polarized the living conditions of the citizens and society. The magnitude and impact of these problems make it even more difficult for individuals, groups, families, and communities to handle unaided thus, necessitating collective intervention and building nexus for communalism and by, groups, local, national, regional, and international bodies for inclusivity. In all of these, the African inclusive ideology and philosophy of "Ubuntu" is multifaceted strong internal mechanisms for promoting general development and safety nets to meet people's needs, and assistance to engender adjustment processes and optimal functioning at the individual, group, family, and community levels. This paper, therefore, adopts a descriptive methodology in examining social collectivism and existentialist (Ubuntu) ideology as a panacea for the improved and sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens in Nigeria.

Theoretical Perspectives to the problem

The Maxims of Existentialist Ideology -Ubuntuism

Maxims according to Obeten (2021), are rules that guide an individual or group of individuals to act and react in a certain way in a given circumstance. Maxims could also be said to be ethical principles guiding and directing individuals or groups to behave in certain ways and manner wherever they find themselves. Ubuntuism is an African philosophical framework that is characterized by the interconnectedness of all things and beings; the spiritual nature of people; their collective/individual

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identity and the collective/inclusive nature of family structure; oneness of mind, body, and spirit; and the value of interpersonal. It promotes collective engagement in problem-solving over individualism, therefore, all actions for the care of vulnerable people must be considered against the backdrop of collectivism.

Externalism connotes that, individuals are responsible for creating purpose or meaning to their own lives and situations. Therefore, creating conditions that promote the growth and sustainable living standards of people, especially the vulnerable people is innate inertia, thus defining our collective existence which is made up of our relationship to other people and things around the world with each choosing and committing to meaning and direction of life. It entails taking decisions or actions that are beneficial and in the best interest of the society. Thus, Ubuntu which is rapidly gaining worldwide acceptance and coverage is based on the following three principles or rules innate in its beliefs (Samkange and Samkange 1980);

1. To be human is to affirm one's humanity by recognizing the humanity of others and on that basis, establish respectful human relations with them. These maxims could be likened to the popular golden rule which says "Do to others what you would like them to do to you".
2. If and when one is faced with a decisive choice between wealth and the preservation of the life of another human being, then one should opt for the preservation of life for its sanctity and sacredness. This is to say; human life remains sacred based on the ubuntu philosophy and by no means or reason should anybody take the life of another or temper with it. This principle is the model of non-violence a component of Ubuntu ideology.
3. The third maxim posits that as a principle deeply embedded in traditional African political philosophy, the king owed his seats, including all the powers associated with it, to the will of the people under him. This maxim speaks volumes of the expected role, duties, and functions leaders in all climes ought to perform. They are the custodians of the people's will and must function and act in the interest of the people. They are indeed leaders to execute resolutions of those they are leading. There cannot be a king, if there are no subjects to be governed. The subjects elect or select the king but then they give their enterprise as subject to the king in words and deeds.

Thus, Ubuntu as a philosophy is associated with words such as sympathy, compassion, benevolence, solidarity, hospitality, generosity, sharing, participation, cooperation, openness, mutuality, affirming, available, kindness, caring, harmony, interdependence, obedience, collectivity and consensus. The term is the opposite of vengeance and the opposite of violence, confrontation, opposite to retribution, and Ubuntu values life, dignity, compassion, humaneness, harmony, and reconciliation (Hailey, 2008; Wichtner-Zoia 2012; Tutu 1997).

Empirical Perspectives to the problem

Ubuntu is an existentialist and a social collectivist approach to mutually sustaining the gains of communalism and inclusiveness in the affairs of the society which gives every member of the society a sense of belongingness. According to Mugumbate and Nyanguru (2013), Ubuntu can best be described as humanism from the African perspective as proposed by Dr. Kenneth Kaunda. Of Zambia, Julies Nyerere Nelson Mandela and Desmond Tutu. Ubuntu is Africa's world view of societal relations, social collectivism, and existentialism. It is a social and humanistic ethic, a prism of enthusiastic social relations and engagement that enhances collectivism. Social collectivism is the capacity in the African culture to express compassion, reciprocity, dignity, cooperation, sympathy, humanity, and interests in bounding members of the society (Khoza 2006:6; Mandela 2006:444; Tutu 1999:34-35). Thus, existentialism and social collectivism in African is seen in the prism of our collective enterprise and implies an appreciation of traditional beliefs, cultural patterns, and distinct practices that have positive impact on our collective lives as a people with diverse cultures and orientations.

Conclusion

Ubuntu ideology within the African soil is a critical mass in human development that promotes inclusiveness and collective enterprise in all environmental and human interactions, activities, and interventions in society. This ideology plays a prominent role in African cultural, political, social, and economic life as well as in managing social problems. As a multidimensional model of development, it guarantees participatory approaches, interconnected in activities and developmental sustainability, and in managing humanitarian emergencies, especially as it affects vulnerable populations, the poor, infirmed, the sick, the deprived, the neglected, the physically and emotionally challenged persons and the less privileged in society. Thus, the vulnerable populations are protected by a systemic network of communal interventions that guarantees them a sense of belonging, welfare, and sustainable livelihood options. This paper, therefore, relied on descriptive methodology to amplify social collectivism and existentialist (Ubuntu) ideology as a panacea for the improved and sustainable standard of living among vulnerable citizens in Nigeria.

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Recommendations

The essence of life generally is to create a better and more formidable front for other humans to strive for. This is the ideological imperative of social collectivism (ubuntu) and the existentialist model to assist, midwife, mitigate, ameliorate, and promote collectivism in all circumstances of interventions.

1. Managing humanitarian crises and interventions should be built on the scale of empathy, integrity, trust, adaptability, and authentic leadership structure that will provide the needed support and results especially when managing vulnerable populations
2. Group dynamics and interconnectedness should be promoted as a strategy for promoting and improving the lives of citizens as well as sustaining the gains and synergy of these social collectivities in driving policy options for addressing the needs of vulnerable populations in Nigeria.
3. Vulnerability is not a curse, therefore, interventions towards vulnerable populations should not be anchored on victimization, favoritism, labeling, and stigmatization rather they should promote affectionate relationships, mutual respect, dignity, competence, confidence, and capacity building that will enhance their adaptation, readjustment, and full functioning as members of the society.

Social collectivism (Ubuntu), in itself is a security mechanism for data and information management in society. Identity and identification of vulnerable citizens are easier to manage within that nucleus; hence, interventions should be specific and center-based within this communal ideology

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